

Synthesis and biological evaluation of new thiophene analogues as potential agents against breast cancer cell lines[†]

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Abstract : A novel series of 3-substituted-2-aminothiophenes 13(a-j) have been synthesized and evaluated for *in vitro* cytotoxic potential against two different breast cancer cell lines such as MCF-7 and T-47-D. Most of the synthesized compounds have shown significant cytotoxicity with IC₅₀ values ranging from 6–45 μM. Among these, compound 13f bearing 3-methoxyphenyl group exhibited highest cytotoxicity against MCF-7 and T-47-D cancer cell line with IC₅₀ values of 7.5 and 6.0 μM, respectively, whereas compound 13b bearing 3-chlorophenyl group showed potent cytotoxic activity against MCF-7 cancer cell line with IC₅₀ = 6 μM value. Compound 13b and 13f might be considered as a potent lead for further development of anticancer agent.

Keywords : SERMs, 2-aminothiophene, cyanoacetamides, carboxamides, MCF-7, T-47-D.

Introduction

Cancer is a malignant neoplasm characterized by the proliferation of abnormal cells that tend to divide in uncontrolled manner, invade surrounding tissue and metastasize to new tissues. Cancer cells have the ability to infiltrate and destroy normal body tissues¹. In recent years, massive efforts for new anticancer agents have been fuelled but cancer is still the second most common cause of death in economically developed countries following heart disease. It is expected that approximately 1,660,290 new cancer cases and 580,350 Americans had die of cancer in 2013, i.e. almost 1,600 people per day². Therefore, there is an urgent need to reveal the new molecular targets and mechanisms by discovery and development of novel therapeutic agents that hamper the progression of malignant tumours and prevent their relapse along with tolerability for normal cells.

Numerous heterocyclic compounds have been reported for the treatment of cancer including indole³, pyrrole⁴, thiophene⁵, benzothiazole⁶, benzimidazole⁷, benzo-

thiophene⁸ etc. Benzothiophenes have displayed interesting anticancer activity as selective estrogen receptor modulators (SERMs), e.g. Raloxifene **1** and Arzoxifene **2** (also act as antitubulin agent) shown in Fig. 1^{9,10}. Raloxifene is frequently prescribed oral selective estrogen receptor modulator (SERM) that has an estrogenic actions on bone and anti-estrogenic actions on the uterus and breast. It is

Fig. 1. Structure of Raloxifene and Arzoxifene.

[†]In honour of Professor K. C. Joshi on the occasion of his 88th birthday.

also used in postmenopausal women to prevent osteoporosis. Along with the antiestrogenic activity, benzothiophenes possess diverse biological functions such as histamine H₃ antagonists¹¹, in Alzheimer's¹², as Rho kinase inhibitors¹³, 5-lipoxygenase inhibitors¹⁴, antihyperglycemic¹⁵, anti-psychotic¹⁶, anti-inflammatory¹⁷ and antiallergic¹⁸.

Some of the benzothiophenes have been investigated as anticancer agents include *N*-methylamino **3**, sulfonyl **4**, and methylene **5** substituted analogues of Raloxifene. These analogues exhibit potent anti-proliferative activity (30–10 nM)¹⁹. In addition, *m*-toluoyl **6**, 4-chlorobenzoyl **7** and *i*-propyl group **8** substituted benzothiophenes also displayed higher binding affinities with ER α and ER β ²⁰. Although, anilides and quinolone substituted benzo[*b*]thiophenes **9** are well known for their significant DNA-binding ability²¹ (Fig. 2).

Despite the significant anti-estrogenic activity of Raloxifene, it has some serious side effects such as mood swing, weakness, tingling, difficulty in vision, dizziness, etc.²². To surmount the side effects and to further explore benzothiophene moiety, we have decided to select Raloxifene as a lead for further structural modifications. These modifications are introduced by increasing the length at 3rd position of thiophene nucleus by inserting amide functionality. Beside this, benzenoid part of the benzothiophene has also been replaced with the saturated carbocyclic ring. In addition, the phenyl ring substitution on 2-position of the thiophene nucleus has been replaced with amino group as shown in Fig. 3. We report herein, the synthesis and cytotoxic evaluation of novel tetrahydro-benzothiophenes against two human breast cancer cell lines such as MCF-7 and T-47-D.

Fig. 2. Benzothiophenes reported for anticancer activity.

Fig. 3. Proposed modifications.

Results and discussion

Chemistry :

The compounds **13(a-j)** were synthesized in two steps. The first step involves the reaction of substituted aniline with ethylcyanoacetate to furnish cyanoacetamides **12(a-j)** (Scheme 1). This reaction involves the nucleophilic attack at carbonyl carbon of ethylcyanoacetate **11** by the aryl amines **10(a-j)** with subsequent removal of ethanol. The cyanoacetamides were obtained smoothly and in high yields. Finally, synthesis of the targeted 2-aminothiophene derivatives **13(a-j)** were obtained by Gewald reaction through condensation reaction of ketone, cyanoacetamides **12(a-j)** and elemental sulphur in presence of diethylamine as catalyst at 60 °C. This reaction mechanism involves the Knoevenagel condensation of an active methylene of nitrile with an oxo component (ketone or aldehyde) to produce an acrylonitrile, which is then thiolated and cy-

clized via nucleophilic attack by sulfur at the cyano carbon to provide an intermediate which undergoes prototropic rearrangement to give 2-aminothiophenes **13(a-j)**. The completion of reaction was monitored by thin layer chromatography and the final compounds were purified by column chromatography.

Biological evaluation :

The newly synthesized compounds **13(a-j)** were screened for their *in vitro* cytotoxic activity against two breast cancer cell lines, namely, MCF-7 and T-47-D cell lines by using MTT (tetrazolium) based viability assay. Docetaxel was used as the standard drug. The MTT assay is a colorimetric assay for measuring the activity of cellular enzymes that reduce the 3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide dye (a yellow tetrazole) to its insoluble formazan, giving a purple color in living cells. The absorbance of this colored solution after 24 h of incubation can be determined by measuring at a certain wavelength (usually between 500 and 600 nm) through ELISA^{23,24}. Drug concentration required to inhibit cancer cell proliferation by 50% (IC₅₀) following incubation of the cells in the culture medium was quantified and the results are summarized in Table 1. The IC₅₀ values obtained for Docetaxel in this assay are 42 μM for MCF-7 and 19 μM for T-47-D.

The *in vitro* screening results revealed that these compounds exhibited encouraging cytotoxic activity with IC₅₀ values ranging from 6 to 45 μM against MCF-7 and 6 to 13 μM against T-47-D cancer cell lines, comparable with the standard Docetaxel. Almost all the compounds ex-

Scheme. 1. Synthesis of targeted compounds **13(a-j)**.

Table 1. Physico-chemical characterization and IC₅₀ values of 2-aminothiophenes **13(a-j)** against MCF-7 and T-47-D cancer cell lines are :

Sr. No.	Compound	R	12(a-j)		13(a-j)		IC ₅₀ Value (μM)	
			Yield (%) ^a	(m.p. °C) ^b	Compound	Yield (%) ^a	MCF-7	T-47-D
1.	12a	C ₆ H ₅	73.6	(115–117)	13a	77.1	9.0	13.0
2.	12b	3-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	64.8	(146–149)	13b	68.1	6.0	15.0
3.	12c	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	66.4	(128–130)	13c	75.4	21.0	12.5
4.	12d	2,4-diCl-C ₆ H ₃	38.4	(117–119)	13d	77.4	8.5	12.0
5.	12e	4-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	64.7	(175–180)	13e	72.8	15.5	12.5
6.	12f	3-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	58.6	(122–126)	13f	63.8	7.5	6.0
7.	12g	4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	73.6	(115–117)	13g	63.6	10.0	8.0
8.	12h	4-OC ₂ H ₅ -C ₆ H ₄	64.8	(146–149)	13h	66.6	45.0	27.0
9.	12i	Pyridin-2-yl	42.7	(172–174)	13i	42.7	9.0	12.0
10.	12j	Naphthalen-1-yl	63.6	(130–132)	13j	63.6	11.0	15.0
11.	Standard	Docetaxel					42.0	19.0

^aIsolated yield. ^bMelting points are uncorrected.

hibit significant cytotoxicity against tested cell lines. Compound **13a** comprising unsubstituted phenyl ring at 3rd position of 2-aminothiophene showed significant cytotoxic activity against MCF-7 and T-47-D cancer cell lines with IC₅₀ values of 9.0 and 13.0 μM. Compound **13c** bearing 4-chlorophenyl group at 3rd position of 2-aminothiophene possess moderate cytotoxic activity against MCF-7 and T-47-D cancer cell lines with IC₅₀ values of 21.0 and 12.5 μM. However, substitution of chlorine group at 3rd position in **13b** enhance the cytotoxic activity against MCF-7 cancer cell line to 3 fold (IC₅₀ = 6 μM), while against T-47-D cancer cell line activity remain constant (IC₅₀ values of 15 μM). Dichloro substituted compound **13d**

showed moderate activity against MCF-7 and T-47-D cancer cell lines with IC₅₀ values of 8.5 and 12.0 μM, higher than monosubstituted compounds **13b** and **13c**. Furthermore, 4-methyl substituted phenyl **13e** was also active against MCF-7 and T-47-D cancer cell lines (IC₅₀ values = 15.5 and 12.5 μM). Compounds **13g** and **13f** bearing 4-methoxyphenyl also possess good cytotoxic activity against MCF-7 and T-47-D cancer cell lines with IC₅₀ values of 10.0, 7.5 μM and 8.0, 6.0 μM, respectively. Compound **13h** bearing 4-ethoxyphenyl group at 3rd position of 2-aminothiophene was active only against T-47-D cell line with IC₅₀ value 27.0 μM. Substitution of heterocyclic ring such as pyridine **13i** and naphthalene ring

13j at 3rd position of 2-aminothiophene displayed significant cytotoxicity against MCF-7 and T-47-D cancer cell lines with IC₅₀ values of 9.0, 11.0 μM and 12.0, 15.0 μM, respectively. Present study showed that on substitution of 4-ethoxyphenyl group at 3rd position of 2-aminothiophene, cytotoxic activity of the compound decreases.

Structure activity relationship :

From the screening results, on MCF-7 cancer cell lines, the cytotoxic activity of compounds **13b** (R = 3-Cl), **13c** (R = 4-Cl), **13f** (R = 3-OCH₃) and **13g** (R = 4-OCH₃) suggest that cytotoxic activity increases in the order of **13b** > **13c** and **13f** > **13g**, which indicates the importance of 3-position of phenyl ring on cytotoxic activity. However, in case of di-chloro substituted compound **13d** activity decreases in the order : **13b** (R = 3-Cl) > **13d** (R = 2,4-diCl) > **13c** (R = 4-Cl). Among the electron-releasing substituted compounds such as **13e**, methyl group at 4-position of phenyl ring exhibited moderate cytotoxic activity and **13h** with ethoxy group did not show good cytotoxic activity. When compared compound **13b** and **13f** (3-chlorine vs 3-methoxy), it was depicted that both compounds displayed excellent cytotoxic activity against MCF-7 cancer cell line. From these results, it is evident that compounds bearing stronger electron-releasing (methoxy) or withdrawing (chlorine) substituents showed improved cytotoxic activity against MCF-7 cancer cell lines. Furthermore, substitution of bulkier or heterocyclic groups such as pyridine **13i** and naphthalene **13j** ring also enhances the activity especially pyridine-2-yl comprising derivative **13i**.

Whereas, SAR studies on T-47-D cell line depicts that electron withdrawing substituted compounds **13b** (R = 3-Cl), **13c** (R = 4-Cl), showed less activity than the electron donating substituted compounds **13f** (R = 3-OCH₃), **13g** (R = 4-OCH₃). However, compound **13e** (R = 4-CH₃) exhibited moderate activity. Among the electron-withdrawing substituted compounds, cytotoxic activity decreases in the order : **13d** (R = 2,4-diCl) > **13c** (R = 4-Cl) > **13b** (R = 3-Cl), that shows the significance of dichloro substituted compounds. Similarly as MCF-7 cancer cell line, compound **13h** with ethoxy group is inactive against T-47-D cancer cell line and compounds bear-

ing bulkier substituted groups such as pyridine **13i** and naphthalene **13j** ring exhibited moderate activity.

Conclusion

In present study, we described the synthesis of 2-aminothiophenes **13(a-j)** through appropriately substituted cyanoacetamides and evaluated for cytotoxic activity in *in vitro* based method. Most of the compounds were synthesized in good yield and purity. Almost all the synthesized compounds **13(a-j)** were active against MCF-7 and T-47-D breast cancer cell lines. The most potent compound was **13f** which possess as significant cytotoxicity against MCF-7 and T-47-D breast cancer cell lines with IC₅₀ values, 7.5 and 6.0 μM, respectively. Another compound **13b** also displayed potent activity against MCF-7 cancer cell line. Based on these encouraging results, further development to synthesize potent compounds is under progress.

Experimental

General :

All the chemicals used in the synthesis were of laboratory grade. The melting points were determined in open capillary method on Buchi-535 electronic apparatus and are uncorrected. The IR spectra of synthesized compounds were recorded on NICOLET-380 FT-IR spectrophotometer in potassium bromide discs. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker AC 300 or 400 MHz spectrometer using TMS (tetramethylsilane) as an internal standard and chloroform as a solvent at SAIF, Punjab University, Chandigarh or IIT, New Delhi. Mass spectra were recorded by Direct Injection method or Electronic Impact (EI) method on GCMS-QP2010 Spectrometer at National Facility for Drug Discovery, Saurashtra University, Rajkot, Gujarat. The progress of the reaction was monitored on silica-gel plates using hexane : ethyl acetate as solvent.

*General procedure for synthesis of compounds N-(substituted-aryl)-2-cyanoacetamide 12(a-j)*²⁵ : A mixture of arylamine (0.0078 mol, 1 g) and ethylcyanoacetate (0.011 mol, 1.25 ml) was refluxed for 4 h in round bottom flask. The reaction mixture was then allowed to cool at room temperature for overnight. The solid obtained was filtered and recrystallized from methanol.

Preparation of 2-cyano-N-phenylacetamide (12a) :

 White color, yield 73.6%, m.p. 115–117 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3053 (C-H stretch, aromatic), 2915 (C-H stretch, aliphatic), 2259 (C≡N), 1669 (C=O), 1610 (C=C).

Preparation of N-(3-chlorophenyl)-2-cyanoacetamide (12b) :

 White color, yield 64.8%, m.p. 146–149 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3082 (C-H stretch, aromatic), 2953 (C-H stretch, aliphatic), 2259 (C≡N), 1667 (C=O), 1593 (C=C).

Preparation of N-(4-chlorophenyl)-2-cyanoacetamide (12c) :

 White color, yield 66.4%, m.p. 128–130 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3084 (C-H stretch, aromatic), 2960 (C-H stretch, aliphatic), 2256 (C≡N), 1667 (C=O), 1612 (C=C); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz, TMS) δ : 3.57 (2H, s), 7.36 (2H, d, J 8.7 Hz), 7.50 (2H, d, J 8.1 Hz), 7.87 (1H, s).

Preparation of N-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)-2-cyanoacetamide (12d) :

 White color, yield 38.4%, m.p. 117–119 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3078 (C-H stretch, aromatic), 2982 (C-H stretch, aliphatic), 2257 (C≡N), 1671 (C=O), 1475 (C=C).

Preparation of 2-cyano-N-p-tolylacetamide (12e) :

 Light brown color, yield 64.7%, m.p. 175–180 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3137 (C-H stretch, aromatic), 2921 (C-H stretch, aliphatic), 2258 (C≡N), 1663 (C=O); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz, TMS) δ : 2.33 (3H, s), 3.54 (2H, s), 7.15–7.16 (2H, d, J 7.8 Hz), 7.37 (2H, d, J 8.1 Hz), 7.66 (1H, s).

Preparation of 2-cyano-N-(3-methoxyphenyl)acetamide (12f) :

 White color, yield 58.6%, m.p. 122–126 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3033 (C-H stretch, aromatic), 2960 (C-H stretch, aliphatic), 2255 (C≡N), 1685 (C=O), 1602 (C=C), 1255 (C=O).

Preparation of 2-cyano-N-(4-methoxyphenyl)acetamide (12g) :

Grey color, yield 63.6%, m.p. 130–132 °C; IR (KBr)

 cm^{-1} : 3099 (C-H stretch, aromatic), 2954 (C-H stretch, aliphatic), 2258 (C≡N), 1658 (C=O), 1616 (C=C), 1255 (C=O).

Preparation of 2-cyano-N-(4-ethoxyphenyl)acetamide (12h) :

 Grey color, yield 66.6%, m.p. 182–184 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3025 (C-H stretch, aromatic), 2978 (C-H stretch, aliphatic), 2259 (C≡N), 1662 (C=O), 1606 (C=C).

Preparation of 2-cyano-N-(pyridin-2-yl)acetamide (12i) :

 Light brown color, yield 42.7%, m.p. 172–174 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3013 (C-H stretch, aromatic), 2949 (C-H stretch, aliphatic), 2260 (C≡N), 1651 (C=O), 1538 (C=C).

Preparation of 2-cyano-N-(naphthalen-2-yl)acetamide (12j) :

 Off white color, yield 63.6%, m.p. 148–151 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3053 (C-H stretch, aromatic), 2917 (C-H stretch, aliphatic), 2257 (C≡N), 1651 (C=O); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz, TMS) δ : 3.65 (2H, s), 7.46–7.54 (3H, m), 7.78–7.93 (4H, m), 8.23 (1H, s).

General synthesis of 2-amino-3-carboxamide thiophenes 13(a-j) : A mixture of cyclohexanone (0.02 mol, 2 ml), cyanoacetamide **12(a-j)** (0.02 mol, 3.9 g) and sulphur (0.02 mol, 0.65 g) and 20 ml of MeOH were taken into a conical flask and heated to 60 °C. Then, while stirring added diethylamine (0.025 mol, 2.6 ml) dropwise, after the addition of base, reaction mixture was stirred for 30 min. Then, the reaction mixture was placed in refrigerator for overnight. The yellow colour precipitates were obtained, filtered and washed with chilled aqueous methanol. The crude compound was purified by column chromatography.

Preparation of 2-amino-4,5,6,7-tetrahydro-N-phenylbenzo[b]thiophene-3-carboxamide (13a) :

White color, yield 77.1%, m.p. 107–109 °C; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{OS}$: C, 66.15; H, 5.92; N, 10.28. Found : C, 66.05; H, 5.99; N, 10.32; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} v : 3245 (N-

Preparation of 2-amino-N-(3-chlorophenyl)-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrobenzo[b]thiophene-3-carboxamide (13b) :

Preparation of 2-amino-N-(4-chlorophenyl)-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrobenzo[b]thiophene-3-carboxamide (13c) :

Preparation of 2-amino-N-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrobenzo[b]thiophene-3-carboxamide (13d) :

Preparation of 2-amino-N-(4-ethoxyphenyl)-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrobenzo[b]thiophene-3-carboxamide (13e) :

White color, yield 72.8%, m.p. 144–146 °C; Anal. Calcd.

Preparation of 2-amino-N-(3-methoxyphenyl)-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrobenzo[b]thiophene-3-carboxamide (13f) :

Preparation of 2-amino-N-(4-methoxyphenyl)-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrobenzo[b]thiophene-3-carboxamide (13g) :

Preparation of 2-amino-N-(4-ethoxyphenyl)-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrobenzo[b]thiophene-3-carboxamide (13h) :

(3H, t, *J* 5.9 Hz), 1.63 (4H, s), 2.53 (2H, s), 2.66 (2H, s), 3.98 (2H, m), 6.82 (2H, d, *J* 7.1 Hz), 7.60 (2H, d, *J* 5.9 Hz), 7.72 (2H, s).

Preparation of 2-amino-4,5,6,7-tetrahydro-N-(pyridin-2-yl)benzo[b]thiophene-3-carboxamide (13i) :

Yellowish brown color, yield 64.2%, m.p. 189–191 °C; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₄H₁₅N₃OS : C, 61.51; H, 5.53; N, 15.37. Found : C, 60.91; H, 5.63; N, 14.91; IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3283 (N-H), 3127 (C-H stretch, aromatic), 2939 (C-H stretch, aliphatic), 1651 (C=O); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz, TMS) δ : 1.60–1.70 (4H, s), 2.52 (2H, s), 2.63 (2H, s), 6.60–7.40 (4H, m), 7.73 (2H, s).

Preparation of 2-amino-4,5,6,7-tetrahydro-N-(naphthalen-1-yl)benzo[b]thiophene-3-carboxamide (13j) :

Off white color, yield 71.2%, m.p. 130–132 °C; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₉H₁₈N₂OS : C, 70.78; H, 5.63; N, 8.69. Found : C, 70.51; H, 5.40; N, 8.50; IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3272 (N-H), 3114 (C-H stretch,

aromatic), 2941 (C-H stretch, aliphatic), 1644 (C=O); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz, TMS) δ : 1.69–1.75 (4H, m), 2.72 (2H, t, *J* 5.7 Hz), 3.07 (2H, t, *J* 5.4 Hz), 7.47–7.60 (4H, m), 8.08–7.84 (4H, m), 8.28 (2H, s); *m/z* 319 [M⁺-2], 219, 180, 143, 127.

Biological assay :

Biological activity can be monitored by using the 3-(4,5-dimethyl-2-thiazolyl)-2,5-diphenyl-2*H*-tetrazolium bromide MTT or MTS assay. This assay measures the reducing potential of the cell using a colorimetric reaction. Viable cells will reduce the MTS reagent to a colored formazan product.

Stock solution (5000 μM/ml) was prepared by dissolving calculated amount of compound in DMSO. Then the different concentrations (50, 25, 12.5 and 6.25 μM) of drug from stock solution (5000 μM) were prepared. MCF-7 and T-47-D cells were plated in 96-multiwell plate (10⁴ cells/well) for 24 h before treatment with the compounds to allow attachment of cell to the wall of the plate, in which cell number was kept at 4000–5000 using Neubauer cell counting chamber. Tested compounds were

dissolved in DMSO and diluted with saline to the appropriate volume. After 24 h of incubation, different concentrations of the compounds under test (6.25, 12.5, 25.0 and 50.0 μM) were added to the cell monolayer. Triplicate wells were prepared for each individual dose. Then cultures were incubated with the compounds for 72 h at 37 °C and in atmosphere of 5% CO₂. After 72 h, cells were fixed, 5 μL of MTT (5 mg/mL in DMSO) was added to each well, and the plate was incubated for a further four hours at 37 °C in dark. The resulting formazan was dissolved in 50 μL dimethyl sulphoxide and absorbance of the solution was read at 595 nm using an ELISA plate reader (Biorad, Model 680, Japan). The relation between surviving fraction and drug concentration was plotted to get the survival curve of each tumor cell line after the specified time. The concentration required for 50% inhibition of cell viability (IC₅₀) was calculated and compared with the reference drug docetaxel. Concentrations of test drugs showing 50% reduction in cell viability (i.e. IC₅₀ values) were calculated using the formula :

$$\% \text{ Cell viability} = \frac{\text{Absorbance (Test)}}{\text{Absorbance (Control)}} \times 100$$

Then calculate the IC₅₀ values by using software Graphpad prism 5.

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Conflict of interest :

The authors have declared no conflict of interest.

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